

Rac-4m

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-55-rac-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	41	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 55 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/5/2022 4:42:37 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/5/2022 7:17:57 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	24.698	2276984	49.71	50669
2	28.266	2303228	50.29	43504

Asy-4m

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	XT-3-56-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0105
Vial:	39	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 56
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	35.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/5/2022 5:21:07 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/5/2022 7:21:21 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	24.663	4216832	96.48	93527
2	28.463	153674	3.52	3340